

FRONTAL EEG ALPHA CHANGES AND COGNITIVE IMPAIRMENT IN THE SUBACUTE MINOR STROKE – PRELIMINARY FINDINGS

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Our aim was to examine the EEG alpha frequency band changes and its relationship to cognitive function in the subacute stroke patients.

We included 5 stroke patients, and 7 healthy controls. Patients were assessed 7-10 days following the right middle cerebral artery (MCA) ischemic stroke. We have measured the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale scores (NIHSS) on admission (9.6 ± 2.61) and on the day of assessment (2.4 ± 1.14) and the Montreal Cognitive Assessment score (MoCA) in stroke patients and healthy controls (18.40 ± 4.88 vs. 27.14 ± 1.68 ; $p=0.003$). EEG was registered with the 21-channel digital system. We analyzed the EEG amplitudes of all conventional frequency bands, the alpha amplitude weighted average frequency (AVG alpha), the group FFT spectra, the group probability density distributions (PDE) and the group phase potentials (PP) and group PP differences per each electrode.

We demonstrated the statistically significant slower alpha at F3, F4 and F8 in the stroke patients vs. controls ($p \leq 0.03$) with no changes of its amplitude ($p \geq 0.08$) which was followed by the augmented delta at F4, and F8 ($p \leq 0.01$), and augmented theta and attenuated beta amplitude at all frontal electrodes ($p \leq 10^{-4}$). We have shown that the frontal and right central cortex (C4, F4, Fp1, Fp2, F7) exhibit greater PP differences than other channels in patients vs. controls. MoCA score was significantly correlated with AVG alpha at F3, F4 and F8 ($p \leq 0.04$).

The slower frontal alpha in the subacute stroke patients is significantly correlated with their cognitive impairment, and its origin colocalizes with the ischemic brain injury.